

OPTIMAL DETERMINATION OF MATERIAL SYMMETRY AXES OF A CARBON-EPOXY COMPOSITE

Christophe ARISTEGUI and Stéphane BASTE
Université Bordeaux I,
Laboratoire de Mécanique Physique, CNRS URA-867,
351, Cours de la Liberation, 33405-Talence Cedex, France.

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the determination of the angular parallax between the geometric coordinate system associated with a sample and the material symmetry coordinate system. The stiffness tensor characteristic of material possessing at least one plane of symmetry, is beforehand obtained by an optimization inversion method. Afterwards the angular parallax is determined by thirteen identified elasticity constants and ultrasonic wave speed measurements. This assessment of the material symmetry coordinate system is tested on experimental data of phase velocities from a Carbon-epoxy composite.

INTRODUCTION

In the case of strongly anisotropic material (wood, composite materials), the traditional mechanical tests are not properly appropriated to the evaluation of all components of stiffness tensor. The ultrasonic characterization usually allows the identification of all stiffness tensor when the material symmetry is orthorhombic [1-4]. This determination always requires the hypothesis of orthorhombic symmetry and the knowledge of the material symmetry axes. In principle, the coincidence of the symmetry axes and of the geometric axes associated with the sample is assumed.

The strata's stacking defects in industrial composite material leads to the disappearance of this coincidence between the material symmetry coordinate system and the geometric coordinate system. In the same way, the annular rings of a wood sample induce the same discordance. Moreover, off-symmetry axes sollicitation creates microcracks with a predominant orientation that does not coincide with the symmetry axes and induce a fully anisotropic degradation. Because of these manufacturing defects, sample cutting or fully anisotropic degradation, a procedure must be developed to identify elasticity coefficients for materials that have no more symmetry planes. In this paper, we investigate the case of the monoclinic symmetry and the recovery of the angular parallax between the geometric coordinate system and the material symmetry coordinate system.

IDENTIFICATION OF THE COEFFICIENTS OF ELASTICITY

In an anisotropic material, three elasticity waves: one quasi-longitudinal and two quasi-shear waves, may propagate with different velocities. These three bulk modes are the solution of the Christoffel equation for an arbitrary propagation direction \mathbf{n} in the material [5]:

$$\det[\Gamma_{ik} - \rho V^2 \partial_{ik}] = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma_{ik} = C_{ijkl} n_j n_k$ is the Green-Christoffel tensor, C_{ijkl} the stiffness tensor, ρ the density, δ_{ik} the Kronecker delta, and V the wave speed of one of the three bulk modes. The usual identification methods depend on all of the experimental data and are then based on non linear optimization procedure [1, 3, 4].

IDENTIFICATION IN THE PRINCIPAL MATERIAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

If the incident plane coincides with a plane of symmetry, only two elasticity waves will be generated in the solid: one longitudinal wave and one shear wave. In this case, Eqn (1) is reduced to a product of a trivial solution and a second degree polynomial in the square of the velocity. The identification methods of stiffness tensor usually take this factorization into account [3]. Thus the study of two principal planes allows us to identify seven coefficients of the stiffness tensor: C_{11} , C_{22} , C_{12} , C_{66} for several different propagation directions in the plane (1, 2) and C_{11} , C_{33} , C_{13} , C_{55} in the plane (1, 3) (Fig. 1). Composite materials are manufactured in thin plates only. It doesn't allow us to investigate the in-plane principal plane (2, 3). The two remaining coefficients C_{23} and C_{44} are identified by the study of the non-principal plane (1, 45°), with Eqn (1).

Therefore, these usual recovery methods require the existence of principal planes relative to orthorhombic symmetry and the knowledge of the material symmetry axes.

Figure 1. Coordinate axes.

GENERALIZATION

To exceed these limits, the identification procedure of stiffness tensor must be generalized to the materials symmetries that are lower than orthorhombic, for example monoclinic or triclinic. The principal or non-principal planes of the different planes of velocity measurements are treated alike. The nine independent elasticity constants for an orthorhombic material must also check the Christoffel equation, Eqn (1), for each data measurement. The functional to minimize is:

$$\min_{(9 C_{ij})} \sum_{V_{exp} \in (\cup 3 \text{ Plans})} f^2((V_{exp}, \mathbf{n}), C_{ij}), \quad (2)$$

$$f((V_{exp}, \mathbf{n}), C_{ij}) = \begin{vmatrix} \Gamma_{11} - \rho V_{exp}^2 & \Gamma_{12} & \Gamma_{13} \\ \Gamma_{12} & \Gamma_{22} - \rho V_{exp}^2 & \Gamma_{23} \\ \Gamma_{13} & \Gamma_{23} & \Gamma_{33} - \rho V_{exp}^2 \end{vmatrix},$$

where V_{exp} are the velocity measurements in the three planes (1, 2), (1, 3) and (1, 45°). Then, all of the stiffness tensor is characterized by only one optimization. A 90% confidence interval is associated with each of the nine independent elasticity constants [5]. The uncertainty of the use of three modes in a principal plane in the previous procedure, Eqn (2), is also raised (Fig. 2). The three slowness curves in each plane are obtained from the nine independent elasticity constants. Solving the Eqn (2) can be represented by the minimization of the deviation between these curves and experimental data. In the optimization process, Eqn (2), information associated with quasi-shear $QT2^{(12)}$ and $QT1^{(13)}$ generated modes provide guidance on the quasi-shear $QT1^{(12)}$ and $QT2^{(13)}$ non-generated modes. The minimization procedure does have the necessary data concerning each generated or non-generated mode, to determine the nine independent elasticity constants.

Figure 2. Slowness curves in the planes (1, 2), (1, 3), (1, 45°) and (2, 3) [6].

To improve the convergence of the simultaneous identification of the nine independent elasticity constants, it is necessary to introduce into the optimization problem the constraints deduced from the thermodynamic requirement. The strict positivity of the material strain energy density ($1/2 C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{ij} \epsilon_{kl}$) induces six constraints g_i ($i=1..6$) [7]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_1 = C_{11} > 0, & & g_2 = \begin{vmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} \end{vmatrix} > 0, & & g_3 = \begin{vmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} \end{vmatrix} > 0. & (3) \\
 g_4 = C_{44} > 0, & & g_5 = C_{55} > 0, & & g_6 = C_{66} > 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

The introduction of the constraints relative to the resolution of a third degree polynomial in the square of the velocity [7] would bring as many constraints as experimental data. To simplify, the only six constraints g_i are considered. Then, Eqn (2) is solved by a constrained optimization method using the lagrangian duality and introducing Lagrangian function [8]:

$$L(C_{ij}, \lambda) = \sum_{v_{exp} \in (\cup 3 \text{ Plans})} f^2(v_{exp}, C_{ij}) + \sum_{i \in [1,6]} \lambda_i (-g_i(C_{ij})), \text{ with } \lambda \in \mathfrak{R}^6. \quad (4)$$

This identification procedure can be equally applied to a material possessing a single plane of symmetry, the plane (2, 3) for example (Fig. 1). Solving the Eqn (2), for no longer nine but thirteen unknown independent elasticity constants, allows us to identify the stiffness tensor of a monoclinic symmetry material:

$$[C_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & C_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ C_{14} & C_{24} & C_{34} & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & C_{56} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{56} & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

There still remains however two features related to this symmetry class. The expressions of the constraints g_4 and g_6 have changed:

$$\varepsilon_6 = \begin{vmatrix} C_{55} & C_{56} \\ C_{56} & C_{66} \end{vmatrix} > 0, \quad \varepsilon_4 = \begin{vmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & C_{34} \\ C_{14} & C_{24} & C_{34} & C_{44} \end{vmatrix} > 0, \quad (6)$$

and four measurement planes of propagation velocity are now required (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Acquisition planes needed to identify monoclinic stiffness tensor.

Figure 4. Diminution of acquisition planes number.

Among the three planes (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 3), only the plane (2, 3) stays a symmetry plane for a monoclinic symmetry material. However, solving the Eqn (2) require data about the principal or non-principal characteristic of planes (1, 2) and (1, 3) considered. The plane (1, 45°) study associated respectively with the study of planes (1, -45°) and (1, 135°) will give these two indications (Fig. 3). Let θ be the angle between the normal to the sample, **1**, and the propagation direction of the incident wave (Fig. 4). The positive incidence in the plane (1, -45°) correspond to the negative incidence in the plane (1, 135°) (Fig. 4). Consequently, if we have access to the positive and negative incidence angles for waves propagating in the plane (1, -45°), the four planes of velocity measurement (1, 2), (1, 3), (1, 45°), (1, -45°) give the data necessary and sufficient to identify the stiffness tensor, Eqn (5).

RESEARCH OF THE PRINCIPAL MATERIAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

Let us focus now on the characterization of a material possessing at least one basis vector of the coordinate system associated with the sample R' , the vector **1'** for instance, normal to a material symmetry plane, for example the plane (2', 3') identical to the plane (2, 3) (Fig. 5). The identified stiffness tensor will have also the form Eqn (5). If there exists a principal material coordinate system R , the studied material will possess the orthorhombic symmetry. This paragraph deals with the research of angular parallax α between R' and R .

Figure 5. R' ($1' = 1, 2', 3'$) coordinate system associated with the sample, R ($1, 2, 3$) the coordinate axes associated with the fibres.

In R' , the material seems to possess the monoclinic symmetry; the stiffness tensor (C'_{ij}), identified in R' , has thirteen independent elasticity constants. Eqn (5). The coordinate system R is the material symmetry axes. If R exists, the material possesses at least an orthorhombic symmetry; the stiffness tensor (C_{ij}), identified in R , will have nine independent elasticity constants. (C'_{ij}) and (C_{ij}) are actually the components of the same tensor C in two different bases connected by a coordinate transformation matrix.

Note that the angular parallax periodicity is $\pi/2$. The angles α and $(\alpha+\pi)$ generate the same coordinate system R , composed of the same three mutually orthogonal planes (1, 2), (1, 3) and (2, 3). If the angular parallax value is $(\alpha+\pi/2)$, the directions 2 and 3, and consequently the planes (1, 2) and (1, 3), permute. The associated coordinate system stays globally equal to R .

Figure 6. Angular parallax periodicity.

FIRST APPROACH OF THE ANGULAR PARALLAX

With (C'_{ij}) and the nine invariants related to a rotation of (C'_{ij}) about the 1-axis [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} & C'_{11}, C'_{12} + C'_{13}, C'_{22} + C'_{33} + 2 C'_{23}, C'_{55} + C'_{66}, C'_{44} - C'_{23}, \\ & C'_{12}C'_{13} - C'_{14}{}^2, C'_{55}C'_{66} - C'_{56}{}^2, (C'_{33} - C'_{22})^2 + 4 (C'_{24} + C'_{34})^2, \\ & C'_{22} + C'_{33} + 2 C'_{23} + 4 (C'_{24} + C'_{34} + C'_{44}), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

the nine components of the stiffness tensor (C_{ij}) relative to R are identified. Let (P_{ij}) $_{\alpha}$ be the coordinate transformation matrix between R' and R :

$$[P_{\alpha}] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\alpha) & \sin(\alpha) \\ 0 & -\sin(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

and the (6x6) transformation matrix (M_{ij}) that depends on (P_{ij}) $_{\alpha}$, the relation [6]:

$$[C] = [M][C'][M]^t, \quad (9)$$

gives the angular parallax value α that will localize R in R' . The angular parallax value is obtained from this estimation, by minimizing a functional that depends on (C'_{ij}) and all of the velocity experimental data.

RECOVERY OF THE ANGULAR PARALLAX

A functional $\mathcal{E}(\partial)$ is built that is minimal for a rotation angle value ∂ equal to the angular parallax α (Fig. 5). If the coordinate system R exists, α will localize it in the coordinate system R' associated with the sample. For each angle value ∂ , a coordinate system R_{∂} ($\mathbf{1}=\mathbf{1}', \mathbf{2}, \mathbf{3}$) is defined. ∂ is also the angle between vectors $\mathbf{2}'$ and $\mathbf{2}$. The stiffness tensor (C_{ij}) $_{\partial}$ relative to the coordinate system R_{∂} is obtained from the relation Eqn (9). The nine (C_{ij}) $_{\partial}$'s components characteristics of orthorhombic symmetry are also introduced in the Christoffel equation, Eqn

(2). Furthermore, for each propagation direction in material, \mathbf{n}' , associated with a velocity measurement collected in R' , a corresponding propagation direction in material, \mathbf{n} , has been defined in R_∂ , with $(P_{ij})_\partial$ coordinate transformation matrix, Eqn (8):

$$[\mathbf{n}] = [P_j]^{-1}[\mathbf{n}'] \quad (10)$$

The expression of the functional is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}(\partial) = \sum_{V_{\text{exp}} \in (\cup 4 \text{ Plans})} f^2\left(\left(V_{\text{exp}}, \mathbf{n}(\partial)\right), 9 C_{ij}(\partial)\right) \quad (11)$$

When a coordinate system related to a stiffness tensor $(C_{\alpha\beta})$ is principal, then the Christoffel determinant, Eqn (1), that depends on experimental measurements of velocity and on the nine components of $(C_{\alpha\beta})$, is zero [6]. Consequently, if α exists, it minimizes also Eqn (11):

$$\alpha = \min_{\partial \in [-\pi/4, \pi/4]} \mathcal{L}(\partial) \quad (12)$$

STIFFNESS TENSOR IN THE PRINCIPAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

The relation Eqn (9) allows the identification of the tensor (C_{ij}) from angular parallax α . However the components C_{14} , C_{24} , C_{34} , C_{56} solutions of the rotation, Eqn (9), can sometimes be different from zero. To find an orthorhombic model, these four characteristics are imposed on the tensor (C_{ij}) . The reason for this divergence are either the non-existence of principal material coordinate system or the perturbations on experimental velocities. Consequently a relative deviation from orthorhombic symmetry is introduced in the following subsection [10].

To associate with (C_{ij}) the same type of 90% confidence interval as the one that is related to (C'_{ij}) 's identification [5], Christoffel equation, Eqn (2), is again resolved in the coordinate system R from experimental measurements of velocity collected in R' . The nine unknown components of the stiffness tensor for an orthorhombic material $(C_{ij})^{\text{optimized}}$ are also identified.

ACCURACY OF THE ANGULAR PARALLAX EVALUATION

Consider the tensors (C_{ij}^0) and $(C_{ij})^{\text{model}}$ computed by a rotation of (C'_{ij}) through an angle α Eqn (9). The tensor $(C_{ij})^{\text{model}}$ verifies the constraints related to a particular model of symmetry. For instance the isotropic model is characterized by nine non-zero elasticity constants and two independent constants. For each hypothesis of symmetry, a relative deviation from model is defined [10]:

$$\Delta_{\text{model}} = \sqrt{\frac{(C_{ijkl}^0 - C_{ijkl}^{\text{model}})^2}{C_{ijkl}^2}} \quad (13)$$

The different deviations from symmetries that are greater than the orthorhombic symmetry, transversely isotropic, isotropic symmetries, will validate the angular parallax value.

ALGORITHM OF THE ANGULAR PARALLAX RECOVERY

Finally, the angular parallax determination can be decomposed into six parts. Firstly the existence of α is supposed. Then an approached value of α is determined using the invariants, relations Eqn (7). From this estimation, the generalized Newton method is applied to the problem, Eqn (9), and gives the optimal value of α . A 90% confidence interval is associated with the optimization solution α [8]. Afterwards, the stiffness tensor (C_{ij}) is reconstructed from (C'_{ij}) , α and Eqn (6). At last the existence of α is discussed from (C_{ij}) and Eqn (10). If R exists, the stiffness tensor $(C_{ij})^{\text{optimized}}$ is identified in R from velocity experimental data collected in R' . An 90% confidence interval is also related to each of the nine elasticity constants of $(C_{ij})^{\text{optimized}}$.

APPLICATION TO AN UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON-EPOXY COMPOSITE

This research of material symmetry axes is tested on a unidirectional Carbon-epoxy composite. The stiffness tensor (C_{ij}) is identified in the coordinate axes R associated with the fibres from velocity measurements collected in planes (1, 2), (1, 3) and (1, 45°).

$$(C_{ij}) = \begin{pmatrix} 11.2 \pm 0.1 & -4.8 \pm 0.1 & 4.1 \pm 0.3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 11.7 \pm 0.1 & 5.2 \pm 0.4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 115.6 \pm 4.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{Sym.} & & 6.6 \pm 0.2 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 5.6 \pm 0.3 & 0 \\ & & & & & 3.3 \pm 0.1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ GPa.}$$

To validate the angular parallax recovery, the carbon-epoxy composite is now identified in a coordinate system R' obtained from a rotation of R through an angle 30° about 1-axis. By considering the velocity measurements collected in planes (1, 2'), (1, 3'), (1, (45°)') and (1, (-45°)'), the stiffness tensor (C'_{ij}) is identified in R'.

$$(C'_{ij}) = \begin{pmatrix} 11.2 \pm 0.1 & 4.0 \pm 0.3 & 4.9 \pm 0.3 & -0.1 \pm 0.2 & 0 & 0 \\ & 15.1 \pm 1.3 & 14.8 \pm 2.3 & 8.9 \pm 1.2 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 80.0 \pm 3.3 & 35.1 \pm 2.2 & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{Sym.} & & 24.7 \pm 1.4 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 5.2 \pm 0.1 & 1.1 \pm 0.1 \\ & & & & & 3.5 \pm 0.1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ GPa.}$$

The study of (C'_{ij}) will allow us to find an angular parallax close to -30° and to reconstruct the stiffness tensor (C_{ij}). The use of invariants relative to the rotation of tensor C_{ij} about 1-axis, gives a first estimation of angular parallax $\alpha_0 = -26.86^\circ$. Then the functional $\mathcal{L}(\vartheta)$ is minimized.

Figure 7. Functional $\mathcal{L}(\vartheta)$.

The use of α_0 as initialization of iterative process implies the convergence of the generalized Newton method towards the angular parallax value:

$$\alpha = -29.47^\circ \pm 0.21^\circ.$$

The stiffness tensors (C^0_{ij}) and (C_{ij})^{model} are defined by the rotation of (C'_{ij}) through an angle α degree about 1-axis. The orthorhombic model is tested (C_{ij})^{model} = (C_{ij})^{OT} amongst others:

$$(C^0_{ij}) = \begin{pmatrix} 11.2 & 4.3 & 4.6 & -0.4 & 0 & 0 \\ & 11.4 & -2.9 & -0.1 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 119.7 & -5.0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{Sym.} & & 7.0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 5.7 & -0.1 \\ & & & & & 3.0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ GPa, } (C^{OT}_{ij}) = \begin{pmatrix} 11.2 & 4.3 & 4.6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 11.4 & -2.9 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 119.7 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{Sym.} & & 7.0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 5.7 & 0 \\ & & & & & 3.0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ GPa.}$$

The different relative deviations from symmetry models Δ_{model} are also defined from the tensor (C^0_{ij}) and the corresponding different tensors (C_{ij})^{model}:

$$\Delta_{\text{orthorhombic}} = 8\%, \quad \Delta_{\text{transversely isotropic}} = 10\%, \quad \Delta_{\text{isotropic}} = 80\%.$$

These weak deviations from the orthorhombic and transversely isotropic model validate the existence of the principal material coordinate system. The classic symmetry of an unidirectional composite is well identified: transversely isotropic symmetry.

In the coordinate system R_α localized by α in R' , the nine components of an orthorhombic model are also identified, resolving again the Christoffel equation. Eqn (2), from velocity measurements collected in planes (1, 2'), (1, 3'), (1, (45°)) and (1, (-45°)):

$$\left(C_{ij}^{\text{optimized}} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} 11.2 \pm 0.1 & 4.8 \pm 0.2 & 4.2 \pm 0.4 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 11.4 \pm 0.3 & 2.7 \pm 1.1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 112.7 \pm 6.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 6.6 \pm 0.1 & 0 & 0 \\ \text{Sym.} & & & & 5.6 \pm 0.1 & 0 \\ & & & & & 3.2 \pm 0.1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ GPa.}$$

We find again with their respective confidence interval, the stiffness tensor (C_{ij}) and angular parallax.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of the angular parallax between the geometric coordinate system associated with the sample and the material symmetry coordinate system has been validated for many materials and whatever the angle value. Because of the uncertainty relative to the experimental data, no test concerning the existence of angular parallax could be exclusively constructed from the thirteen components of the stiffness tensor (C'_{ij}). That's why, we suppose the existence of the principal material coordinate system and then we discuss the validity of the tensor (C_{ij}) identified in this coordinate system.

This research of material symmetry axes will find its application in the description of the fully anisotropic degradation. This degradation can be decomposed into three levels: (i) diminution of the stiffness in the coordinate axes R associated with the fibres, without rotation of R . (ii) rotation of R . (iii) the orthogonality property of R disappears. This paper deals with the second step. The study of (iii) is still to be developed to measure the full anisotropic damage of material subject to off-axis solicitation [11].

REFERENCES

1. J. Roux and B. Hosten and B. Castagnède and M. Deschamps, Caractérisation mécanique des solides par spectro-interférométrie ultrasonore, *Rev. Phys. Appl.*, **20**, 351-358 (1985).
2. S. Baste and B. Hosten, Evaluation de la matrice d'élasticité des composites orthotropes par propagation ultrasonore en dehors des plans principaux de symétrie, *Rev. Phys. Appl.*, **25**, 161-168 (1990).
3. B. Castagnède and W. Sachse, Optimized determination of elasticity constants of anisotropic solids from wavespeed measurements, *Review of progress in QNDE*, **8b**, 1855-1862 (1989).
4. Y. C. Chu and S. I. Rokhlin, Stability of determination of composite moduli from velocity data in planes of symmetry for weak and strong anisotropies, *J.A.S.A.*, **95**, 213-225 (1994).
5. B. Audoin and S. Baste and B. Castagnède, Estimation de l'intervalle de confiance des constantes d'élasticité identifiées à partir des vitesses de propagation ultrasonores, *Comp. Rend. Acad. Sci. Paris*, **312 b**, p679-686 (1991).
6. B. A. Auld, Acoustic fields in solids, *Wiley-Interscience*, New York, Vol 1 (1973).
7. R. G. Payton, Elasticity wave propagation in transversely isotropic media, *Martinus Nijhoff publishers* (1983).
8. A. Gourdin and M. Boumahrat, Méthodes numériques appliquées, *Lavoisier*, Paris, France (1983).
9. T. C. T. Ting, Invariants of anisotropic elasticity constants, *Quarterly J. Mech. Appl. Math.*, **40**, 431-448 (1987).
10. R. J. Artz, A study of general anisotropic elasticity in rocks by wave propagation, *PH.D. dissertation*, Université Paris VI (1994).
11. S. Baste and B. Audoin, On internal variables in anisotropic damage, *Eur. J. Mech. A/Solids*, **10**, n° 6, 587-606 (1991).